

Assessment of Clinical Profile and Outcome of Upper Gastrointestinal Bleed in Patients with Liver Cirrhosis: A Prospective Study in a Tertiary Care Hospital in Northeast India

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Abstract:

Background: Upper gastrointestinal (GI) bleeding is a common and life-threatening complication in patients with liver cirrhosis. It is primarily caused by variceal bleeding due to portal hypertension or non-variceal causes such as gastroduodenal ulcers. Despite advancements in diagnostic and therapeutic strategies, upper GI bleeding remains a major contributor to morbidity and mortality in cirrhotic patients, necessitating comprehensive evaluation and management.

Aim: To assess the clinical profile and outcomes of upper GI bleeding in patients with liver cirrhosis and identify the variceal and non-variceal etiologies to guide effective management strategies.

Methods: This prospective observational study was conducted at the Department of Gastroenterology, Gauhati Medical College and Hospital, from March 2023 to April 2024. A total of 128 cirrhotic patients presenting with upper GI bleeding were included. Data on clinical features, endoscopic findings, treatment outcomes, and in-hospital mortality were collected and analyzed. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0.

Results: Among the 128 patients, 92 (71.9%) had variceal bleeding, predominantly esophageal varices, while 36 (28.1%) had non-variceal bleeding, mainly gastroduodenal ulcers. Anemia was the most common complication (87.5%), followed by renal failure (43.7%). The in-hospital mortality rate was 12.5%, primarily in patients with severe variceal bleeding. Alcoholism was the leading cause of cirrhosis (49.3%), followed by MASH (21.9%). Endoscopic variceal ligation (EVL) was the primary intervention in variceal cases, while ulcers were managed with standard endoscopic therapies.

Conclusion: Upper GI bleeding in cirrhotic patients is a critical condition with significant morbidity and mortality. Variceal bleeding remains the predominant cause, often associated with poor outcomes. Early diagnosis, prompt intervention, and targeted management strategies are essential to improve survival and reduce complications.

Recommendations: Efforts should focus on preventive strategies, including early screening for high-risk varices and lifestyle modifications to reduce alcohol-induced liver damage. A multidisciplinary approach and adherence to evidence-based protocols are crucial for optimizing patient outcomes.

Keywords: Upper gastrointestinal bleeding, Liver cirrhosis, Variceal bleeding, Portal hypertension, Endoscopic management.

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Introduction

Upper gastrointestinal (GI) bleeding is a serious medical emergency and a significant cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide, particularly in patients with liver cirrhosis. The prevalence of cirrhosis-related GI bleeding has risen in recent years due to increasing alcohol consumption and viral hepatitis in many regions [1,2]. This bleeding is commonly classified into variceal and non-variceal bleeding, with variceal bleeding,

predominantly from esophageal varices, being the most frequent cause in cirrhotic patients. Portal hypertension, a hallmark of liver cirrhosis, leads to the formation of these varices, which carry a high risk of rupture, with a mortality rate of 20%–30% per episode [3].

Non-variceal upper GI bleeding, although less common in cirrhosis, primarily results from

gastroduodenal ulcers or mucosal lesions. Such bleeding is often exacerbated by coagulopathy and thrombocytopenia inherent in cirrhosis, complicating management and increasing the risk of adverse outcomes [4]. Advances in endoscopic techniques, pharmacological interventions, and improved critical care have significantly enhanced the prognosis of upper GI bleeding over the last decade [5].

The diagnosis and management of gastrointestinal bleeding heavily relies on endoscopic treatments. With excellent success rates and lowered chances of rebleeding, endoscopic variceal ligation (EVL) is a common method for treating variceal hemorrhage [6]. Furthermore, somatostatin analogs and terlipressin are examples of vasoactive medications that are frequently used to lower portal pressure and manage active bleeding [7]. Given the elevated risk of infection, which can exacerbate results, antibiotic prophylaxis is crucial for cirrhotic patients [8].

Reducing the morbidity and mortality linked to gastrointestinal bleeding requires the implementation of preventive measures. For patients with high-risk esophageal varices, EVL and non-selective beta-blockers are advised as the main preventive measures. Beta-blockers and repeat endoscopic therapy have been shown to be a successful combination for secondary prophylaxis, preventing rebleeding [9]. Patients with uncontrolled bleeding, however, continue to have a poor prognosis, requiring increasingly sophisticated procedures such as the implantation of a transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt (TIPS) [10].

Despite these advancements, upper GI bleeding remains a leading cause of hospital admissions and mortality in cirrhotic patients. A multidisciplinary approach involving gastroenterologists, hepatologists, and critical care specialists is crucial for optimizing outcomes. Further research into newer therapeutic modalities and strategies to improve early diagnosis and management is essential to reduce the burden of this life-threatening complication.

Methodology

Study Design: This was a prospective observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted in the Department of Gastroenterology at Gauhati Medical College and Hospital, a tertiary care hospital located in Guwahati, Assam, India. The hospital caters to a diverse population, making it an ideal setting for such a study.

Participants: The study included 128 patients with upper gastrointestinal hemorrhage and cirrhosis. Using predetermined inclusion and exclusion criteria, these subjects were progressively recruited over the study period.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Patients of both sexes aged 18 years and above.
2. Individuals presenting with upper GI bleeding and having a confirmed diagnosis of chronic liver disease.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients without a confirmed diagnosis of liver cirrhosis.
- Patients unwilling or unable to provide informed consent.

Bias: During the study period, all eligible patients who met the criteria were included in the successive sampling process to reduce selection bias. Protocols and consistent data collection techniques helped to reduce observer bias.

Data Collection: A structured proforma was used to collect the data. It contained clinical presentation, patient demographics, laboratory investigations, endoscopic findings, treatment outcomes, and in-hospital mortality rates. Detailed history, including alcohol use and prior episodes of GI bleeding, was also recorded.

Procedure: All patients underwent a thorough clinical examination and endoscopic evaluation to determine the cause of the upper GI bleed. The primary focus was to differentiate variceal from non-variceal causes. Treatment interventions, including blood transfusion and pharmacological or endoscopic therapies, were recorded. Outcomes were assessed in terms of resolution of bleeding, complications such as anemia and renal failure, and in-hospital mortality.

Statistical Analysis: Data analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics summarized clinical and demographic features, with means and standard deviations for continuous variables and frequencies and percentages for categorical variables. Comparative studies assessed correlations between GI bleeding etiologies and clinical outcomes, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

Table 1: Participant Demographics

Characteristic	Value
Total Participants	128
Male	80 (62.5%)
Female	48 (37.5%)
Mean Age (years)	48.6 ± 12.3
Age Range (years)	18–75

128 patients with upper (GI) bleeding and liver cirrhosis were recruited for the study. The mean age was 48.6 ± 12.3 years, and the majority were male (62.5%).

Table 2: Causes of Upper GI Bleeding

Cause of GI Bleeding	Number of Patients (n)	Percentage (%)
Variceal Bleeding	92	71.9
Non-variceal Bleeding	36	28.1

The predominant cause of GI bleeding was variceal bleeding (71.9%), primarily esophageal varices and non-variceal causes were seen in 28.1% of patients.

Table 3: Clinical Outcomes

Outcome	Number of Patients (n)	Percentage (%)
Anemia	112	87.5
Renal Failure	56	43.7
Shock	40	31.2
Hepatic Encephalopathy	48	37.5
Mortality	16	12.5

Anemia was the most common complication, followed by renal failure and hepatic encephalopathy. These outcomes underscore the critical need for prompt intervention.

Table 4: Etiology of cirrhosis

Cause of Cirrhosis	Number of Patients (n)	Percentage (%)
Alcoholism	63	49.3
MASH	28	21.9
Hepatitis B	14	10.9
Autoimmune hepatitis	12	9.4
Hepatitis C	7	5.4
Cryptogenic	4	3.1

Alcoholism was the leading cause of cirrhosis, affecting nearly half of the study population.

Table 5: Endoscopic Findings

Endoscopic Findings	Number of Patients (n)	Percentage (%)
Esophageal Varices	73	57.0
Gastric Varices	19	14.8
Gastroduodenal Ulcers	21	16.4
PHG	7	5.5
GAVE	6	4.7
Mallory Weiss tear	1	0.8
Esophageal malignancy	1	0.8

Endoscopic evaluation showed that esophageal varices were the most common finding, followed by gastric varices and gastroduodenal ulcers.

Interpretation of Findings

- Variceal Bleeding** was the predominant cause, correlating with the presence of portal hypertension.
- Anemia** was the most frequent complication, reflecting significant blood loss during GI bleeding episodes.

- Alcohol-induced Cirrhosis** was the primary underlying etiology, emphasizing the need for public health interventions.

- Endoscopic Evaluation** plays a critical role in identifying the source of bleeding and directing appropriate management strategies.

Discussion

This study involving 128 patients with upper gastrointestinal (GI) bleeding and liver cirrhosis revealed that the majority were middle-aged males (mean age 48.6 years, 62.5% male). Variceal bleeding, primarily from esophageal varices, was the

leading cause (71.9%), strongly linked to portal hypertension, while non-variceal causes like gastroduodenal ulcers accounted for 28.1%. Alcoholism was identified as the predominant etiology of cirrhosis (49.3%), followed by metabolic-associated steatohepatitis (MASH) and viral hepatitis. Anemia was the most common complication (87.5%), alongside renal failure (43.7%) and hepatic encephalopathy (37.5%), with a mortality rate of 12.5%, reflecting the severity of the condition. Endoscopic findings confirmed esophageal varices as the most frequent source of bleeding, underscoring the role of endoscopy in guiding diagnosis and management. These results highlight the need for targeted interventions, including public health measures to address alcohol abuse, routine screening for portal hypertension, and prompt treatment strategies to improve outcomes in this high-risk population.

Upper gastrointestinal bleeding (UGIB) remains a significant clinical challenge in patients with liver cirrhosis, with outcomes heavily influenced by the type of bleeding and the severity of liver dysfunction. Prognostic scoring systems, such as the Child-Turcotte-Pugh (CTP), MELD, and other derived scores, have shown utility in predicting in-hospital outcomes. A study validating these scores highlighted that while the Child-Pugh score and Clinical Rockall Score (CRS) were effective in predicting in-hospital rebleeding, MELD-Na and AIMS65 scores were particularly effective at predicting in-hospital mortality in patients with variceal bleeding. This underscores the importance of integrating multiple scoring systems in clinical decision-making [11]. Nonvariceal UGIB also poses substantial risks. Outcomes from a nationwide analysis revealed that decompensated cirrhosis is associated with higher rates of 30-day readmission, prolonged hospitalization, and increased mortality compared to compensated cirrhosis. Delayed esophagogastroduodenoscopy (EGD) was identified as a modifiable risk factor contributing to poorer outcomes, emphasizing the need for timely interventions [12]. Comparisons of UGIB in cirrhotic versus non-cirrhotic populations have demonstrated that cirrhotics are more likely to experience variceal bleeding and rebleeding episodes. A retrospective study revealed that 85% of cirrhotic patients hospitalized with UGIB had upper gastrointestinal involvement, with rebleeding rates significantly higher compared to non-cirrhotics [13]. Similarly, variceal bleeding in decompensated cirrhotics resulted in longer hospital stays and higher readmission rates, though mortality did not significantly differ from nonvariceal bleeding. This suggests that clinical management and supportive care remain pivotal in improving outcomes [14].

Similarly, Gatta et al. developed a prognostic index for mortality prediction in cirrhotic patients with

UGIB. Key predictors included serum creatinine, bilirubin levels, and the presence of ascites, demonstrating the utility of accessible clinical parameters in outcome prediction [15]. Lyles et al. further emphasized the significance of prognostic tools, introducing a scoring system based on parameters like MELD score, serum albumin, and the use of vasoactive agents. This scoring system outperformed traditional methods like the Rockall score in predicting in-hospital mortality [16]. Afessa and Kubilis reported that systemic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS) and organ failure were prominent predictors of mortality in hospitalized cirrhotic patients with UGIB. These findings underline the complexity of managing critically ill patients [17]. Finally, Prasad et al. provided evidence from South India that variceal bleeding (35.9%) surpassed peptic ulcers as the leading cause of UGIB in cirrhotic patients. Despite therapeutic advancements, the recurrence rate of bleeding was 11.9%, and mortality remained at 8.6%, emphasizing the need for better preventive and therapeutic strategies [18].

Conclusion

The study highlights the burden of upper GI bleeding in cirrhotic patients, predominantly driven by variceal bleeding and alcohol-related cirrhosis. Early diagnosis, endoscopic evaluation, and targeted management of underlying etiologies are critical to improving patient outcomes and reducing mortality. These findings advocate for preventive measures against alcoholism and enhanced clinical protocols for managing upper GI bleeding in cirrhotic patients.

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